

RISK AND RISK-TAKING IN SMALL BUSINESS ACTIVITIES

Teacher: O'ktamjonova Zulayho

Fergana Polytechnic Institute, Fergana, Uzbekistan

Student: Yuldashev Muzaffarbek Jakbaraliyevich

Fergana Polytechnic Institute, Fergana, Uzbekistan

Student: Abdumutalov Otabek Rozmatjonovich

Fergana Polytechnic Institute, Fergana, Uzbekistan

ABSTRACT.

In this article, small business operations usually have small financial resources compared to large corporations, and such businesses are subject to constant changes in security, economic viability, and other typical risks. A business owner should try to reduce risk, but only through their own personal trading strategies and organizational risk. This is very important in paying off debts and developing new businesses. Also, a business owner can take risks to grow and improve, while also taking risks in compliance, to win. In such a case, it is important for the business owner to understand and learn against future risks and deadlines, and to be prepared to address any issues in depth.

Keywords. *Technology, small business, change, risk, advertising, risks.*

Risk and risk in small business activities can exist in different forms. Business-related risks are typical:

Sources through the organization: Buyers or producers do not provide security to cash when they are given it.

Price interaction: In any sector, prices can have different effects on each other. Price increases or decreases can affect your business analysis strategy.

Technologies: Technological changes make business easier, but can also increase homogeneity. Small business operations may be affected by technological failures.

Changing markets: can open the way to like former customers, bring new and sales organizations, increase reputations, and have a clear effect on product quality satisfaction and other reasons.

Similar to the risks involved in small business operations, risk management can help mitigate these risks. This includes processes such as real-time analysis of other projects, implementation of a viable marketing strategy, and product quality

improvement. Compared to this, before doing good organization and projects to overcome risks in small business activities, we need to maintain good relationships and calculations and save the hitchhiker capital for trading.

Risk and risk in small business activities mainly affect the way of creation, introduction, and development of business. Risk and risk are mutually exclusive balances. For example, risks related to business activities (financial, commercial, technological, etc.) can affect the development of business in the international market.

Small businesses are different from large businesses because their financial resources are limited in their availability. Implementing strategies, determining the demand for specific products, analyzing sales figures, and taking risks in decision-making greatly increase the stability of the processes of establishing a modern enterprise.

Risk in small business operations is quite simple to understand because there is no such thing as risk-free for any business. As with starting a business, preparing, selling, and marketing services or products, and many other tasks, and maintaining popular and familiar accounts, small businesses need activities that use supports that call on various challenges that have arisen in their experience.

Risk-taking is one of the important characteristics in business activities because every day there are new challenges and problems in business. Small business success requires more than just minimizing risk. In particular, the position and size of the business should be considered, and before proceeding with leasing, loans, and other financial issues, it is possible to try to obtain domestic and on-demand breeding to achieve success in small business operations.

The launched strategy is colorful, focusing on simple calculations in business activities, changing the business language among customers and business and trade organizations, implementing advertising campaigns, and improving the quality of sales. implementation of direct processes can free businesses from dangerous situations in the international market.

CONCLUSION

For a small business owner, the concept of risks and other important aspects should be understood. It should try to attract additional financial resources by improving relationships and using business cycles. In addition, the business owner cannot solve all his problems, so he must be more responsible and remove everything from his other work, such as amenities, marketing strategies, beauty, and various commercial strategies. To proceed, every business must take risks instead of taking risks for its benefit, but the disadvantages of this do not require much attention, besides, more than one can imagine, it is necessary to use organizational measures.

REFERENCES:

1. World Bulletin of Management and Law (WBML) Available Online at: <https://www.scholarexpress.net> Volume-19, February-2023 ISSN: 2749-3601 PRINCIPLES OF ORGANIZATION OF BENCHMARKING SERVICE IN INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES Zulayxo Uktamjonova Assistant, Department of Management, Fergana Polytechnic Institute, Fergana, Uzbekistan
2. Расулов, Р., Сатторов, А., & Махкамова, Д. (2022). Вычисление Квадрат Нормы Функционала Погрешности Улучшенных Квадратурных Формул В Пространстве. Central asian journal of mathematical theory and computer sciences, 3(4).
3. O'zbekiston Respublikasida kichik va o'rta biznes korxonalari rivojlanishining asosiy ko'rsatkichlari. -T.: Davlat Mulk qo'mitasi, 2001.
4. Rashidjon, R., & Sattorov, A. (2021). Optimal Quadrature Formulas with Derivatives in the Space. Middle European Scientific Bulletin, 18.
5. UO'K 338.1.001.76 XORAZM MA'MUN AKADEMIYASI AXBOROTNOMASI -3/2-2023 SANOAT KORXONALARIDA BENCHMARKINGNI TASHKIL QILISH ZARURIYATI Z.A.Uktamjonova, o'qituvchi, Farg'ona politexnika instituti, Farg'ona
6. Rasulov, R. ., Sattorov, A. ., & Mahkamova, D. T. . (2022). View of the Derivative Quadrature Formula Norm in Space . Modern Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities, 10.
7. World Bulletin of Management and Law (WBML) Available Online at: <https://www.scholarexpress.net> Volume-19, February-2023 ISSN: 2749-3601 PRINCIPLES OF ORGANIZATION OF BENCHMARKING SERVICE IN INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES Zulayxo Uktamjonova Assistant, Department of Management, Fergana Polytechnic Institute, Fergana, Uzbekistan E-mail: zulayxoaminjonova@gmail.com
8. Хусанов Ю. Ю., Таштанов Х. Н. Ў., Сатторов А. М. Машина деталлари пармалаб ишлов бериладиган нотехнологик юзалар турлари //Scientific progress. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 1. – С.
9. Husanov Y. Y., Abdullayev S. M., Sattorov A. M. MEXATRONIKA VA ROBOTOTEXNIKADA VIRTUAL LABARATORIYALARDAN FOYDALANISH //Scientific progress. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 7. – С.
10. O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASI OLIY VA O'RTA MAXSUS TA'LIM VAZIRLIGI TOSHKENT DAVLAT IQTISODIYOT UNIVERSITETI D. RASULEV, SH. NURULLAYEVA, N. RO'ZMETOVA, M. MUMINOVA BIZNES-JARAYONLARINI MODELLASHTIRISH O'quv qo'llanma